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The Open Energy Knowledge Graph

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1 Motivation: The challenge of uniformly describing energy scenarios

Energy and climate scenarios are inherently intertwined with complex technological or socio-economic factors. The main goal of these scenarios is to envision the future of energy systems and discuss the necessary conditions to achieve specific climate or environmental targets. Energy researchers use a broad range of assumptions, parameters, and modelling methodologies to develop their scenarios. This leads to the development of multiple studies and scenarios with different objectives and levels of detail [1]–[4]. Unfortunately, the documentation and publication of scenarios usually fail to adhere to transparency and interoperability standards. Hence, analyzing and comparing studies and scenarios becomes a cumbersome manual task. For example, a lot of effort is needed to pre-process and harmonize data from several energy scenarios before an actual comparison can take place. To address these issues, we introduce the Open Energy Knowledge Graph (OEKG), which allows users to conveniently describe, upload, explore, and compare different energy scenarios and projection data based on multiple factors.

2 A knowledge graph based on the Open Energy Ontology

To tackle the challenge of uniformly describing energy scenarios, a harmonized terminology and logical structure is required. The Open Energy Ontology (OEO)[5] is a domain ontology for energy system analysis, which defines important concepts of the energy domain and their logical relations. It provides a standardized interrelated vocabulary upon which the OEKG is built. While the OEO functions on a conceptual level, the OEKG operates at an instance level, providing factual information about concrete examples of the concepts defined in the OEO.

With the OEKG we are thus able to establish connections among different stakeholders to facilitate effective collaboration and information sharing.

3 Semantic structure of the OEKG

The factual information in the OEKG can be extended and validated based on the conceptualization defined by the OEO. As with the development of ontologies, building a knowledge graph with an underlying semantic schema demands continuous dedication and commitment. In this respect, Figure 1 displays the interaction between the Open Energy Knowledge Graph and Open Energy Ontology.

As an example, at the conceptual level, the OEO contains logical axioms such as *Solar power technology* \sqsubseteq *Power generation technology* \sqsubseteq *Energy technology* stating that *Solar power technology* is a kind of *Power generation technology*, which in turn is a kind of *Energy technology*.

Accordingly, at the instance level, the OEKG contains a factual statement for a particular case such as *Covers technology* (*Example_study*, *Solar power technology*) which states a specific scenario bundle with the label *Example_study* contains the *Solar power technology* as one of its considered technologies.

Figure 1. The connection between OEKG and OEO

4 Application: Scenario Bundles for the description and comparison of energy scenarios

The Open Energy Knowledge Graph (OEKG) lays the foundation for the so-called Scenario Bundles on the Open Energy Platform (OEP). Scenario Bundles connect various data related to energy studies and scenarios, encompassing items such as abstracts, authors, associated institutions, utilized models, published data tables, and the meta-data about datasets. These connections are depicted in Figure 1. Scenario Bundles offer several benefits: (1) They help to explore, compare, and add information about climate and energy scenarios and their projections. (2) Researchers have the opportunity to present their contributions and help build a larger and searchable knowledge base, open to the public. (3) Policy makers will be able to browse available information in an intuitive way that helps them make sense of the wealth of available information. Figure 2 shows an example Scenario Bundle that is created via the Open Energy Platform. While Bundles are shown as user-friendly web-based forms, in the background, each Bundle corresponds to a sub-graph within the OEKG. These sub-graphs can have *shared* parts. The OEKG also allows to compare scenario information. Figure 3 presents an example comparison based on various qualitative aspects between three different Scenario Bundles. Elements in Scenario Bundles are associated with a specific concept in the OEO. These assigned concepts enable the comparison illustrated in Figure 3.

Consolidated and Harmonised GHG Emission Projections from European Legislation	
Acronym	CHGHG
Contact person(s)	Hannah Förster · Christian Winger ·
Institutions	Öko-Institut e.V. ·
Funding sources	Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz ·
Descriptors	Greenhouse gas emissions · CO2 emissions ·
Abstract	We compiled data and harmonised their notation for GHG emission projection data that European Member States submit under European Legislation mandatorily every two years (and voluntarily in between). The series of tables starts from the GHG emission projections submitted by European Member States in 2014 and is amended as new data becomes available in the reporting platform. (These datasets have the suffix <code>_eio</code> or <code>_rep</code>). The purpose of providing these compilations is to enable straight forward data comparison across the whole series of submissions. We also harmonised data notation across all available submission years for the same datasets but quality checked and approved and compiled by the European Environment Agency (EEA). For these datasets we harmonised data notation across the whole series (These datasets have the suffix <code>_eea</code>).

Scenarios (3)		Publications	Sectors and technology	Models and frameworks
Name	With existing measures scenario			
Acronym	WEM			
Abstract	A with existing measures scenario (WEM) is a policy scenario that includes policy instruments and transformative measures that have been adopted and implemented. The WEM scenario is a mandatory reporting requirement for European Member States, according to European legislation (the latest being the EU Governance Regulation). The datasets provided on the OEP include all European Member States at the submission year. For example, data for the United Kingdom is not available in any datasets submitted after Brexit. For ease, the countries below include all current and former EU Member States. The datasets (suffix <code>_eio</code>) provided includes the WEM scenario data only for those Member States who provided that data.			
Descriptors	with existing measures scenario · emission scenario · greenhouse gas emission scenario · policy scenario · CO2 emission scenario ·			
Years	2030 · 2020 · 2040 · 2050 · 2025 · 2035 · 2045 ·			

Figure 2. A scenario bundle

5 Technical details

An instance of Apache Jena Fuseki[6], which serves as a SPARQL[7] server, stores factual information about scenario bundles. All web-based tools for creating, editing, exploring, and comparing scenario bundles are unified in the Open Energy Platform¹. To manage user interactions, we used the React[8] framework. Backend functionalities such as API requests and user permissions are developed using the Django[9] frame-

¹<https://openenergy-platform.org/scenario-bundles/main>

Figure 3. Scenario comparison. Greens: matching items. Reds: differences. A scenario bundle is considered as the base (left-hand side), and others are then compared to it.

work. We used the RDFLib[10] library to produce RDF[11] triples based on user inputs. All of these tools are open-sourced² and online documentations are available for the semantic structure³ and the developers' guide⁴.

6 Future work

Our focus is on promoting transparency and interoperability among energy scenarios. To build a vibrant community around the Open Energy Knowledge Graph, we have a strong emphasis on user participation. In our upcoming work, we plan to enhance the OEKG with additional factual information and introduce new features to the Open Energy Platform, such as a comprehensive history that keeps track of the changes that are made by users in scenario bundles.

Moreover, quantitative comparison of scenario projections is not always directly feasible since various datasets have different units, starting points, and trajectories. Also, organizations often focus on specific geographical regions. Therefore, it is essential to consider these regional and temporal differences when analyzing and comparing energy scenarios. To address these challenges, we are developing an Ontology-Based Data Integration (OBDI) system that enables users to quantitatively compare various energy and climate scenarios.

Furthermore, our efforts are directed towards the dissemination of information within the community and ensuring that valuable resources are easily accessible. To accomplish this goal, we aim to cultivate strong and effective connections with other well-established knowledge graphs, such as the Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG)[12], [13].

²<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform>

³https://openenergyplatform.github.io/organisation/family_members/knowledge-representation/oekg/#structure

⁴<https://openenergyplatform.github.io/oeplatform/install-and-documentation/oeplatform-code/web-api/oekg-api/>

As previously stated, our knowledge graph is constructed using the OEO as its core schema⁵. Therefore, the ongoing enhancement of our knowledge graph is closely tied to the continuously evolving process of ontology development. While our knowledge graph is designed to remain adaptable as the ontology terminology evolves, comparing energy scenarios based on ontological similarity is still a difficult task. This difficulty stems from the intricate nature of the energy domain, which encompasses technological, regional, and political complexities. Therefore, it will be necessary to establish more complex relations between the concepts in the Open Energy Ontology and reflect these connections in the Open Energy Knowledge Graph.

7 Limitations

Currently, comparing scenario bundles involves inspecting the OEO concepts associated with the elements in the bundles and determining whether two elements from different bundles share the same OEO concept. This approach provides a simple form of comparison. However, a more sophisticated comparison could introduce a similarity metric based on the ontological distance or similarity between the concepts. Developing a comprehensive similarity metric requires in-depth knowledge about the energy domain along with proficiency in ontologies and knowledge engineering. We will tackle this issue in our future efforts.

At present, our ability to create a precise and organized knowledge graph relies on the information provided by users. This process is slow and therefore, limits the extent to which factual information can be integrated into the OEKG. We are currently working on creating an automated pipeline to integrate additional factual information into the OEKG. This involves gathering metadata from the data tables available on the Open Energy Platform. However, valuable information about datasets is often spread out across multiple data tables. As a result, a normalization step is indispensable before integrating information about datasets into the OEKG.

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⁵The OEKG also utilizes other ontologies, for instance, we use the LCC ontology for the country names, which is available at <https://www.omg.org/spec/LCC/>

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